

Influence of Kinetic Models on the Simulation of Frontal Polymerization

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Frontal Polymerization:

- Fast & energy efficient
- Longer pot-life

? → study with modelling methods

- Require precise balance of heat
 - *Premature (bulk) polymerization*
 - *Quenching of fronts*
- Instabilities
 - *Comes from rapid change of temperature & properties*

Reaction kinetics model:

Phenomenological

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(1 - \alpha)^n$$

n-th order

α : conversion

Mechanistic

$$\frac{d[C]}{dt} = k[A][B]$$

Phenomenological compared to mechanistic:

Less computation resource required

Less explanatory in mechanism, rely more on experimental data

Parameters are specific to a single formulation

Aim of this study: Propose a rational mechanistic kinetic model for **radical induced cationic polymerization (RICP)** and implement to a frontal polymerization simulation.

Mechanistic kinetic models with FP simulation:

Goldfeder, P. M., et al. (1997): free radical polymerization

Bistri, Donald, et al. (2024): ring-opening metathesis polymerization

Radical induced cationic polymerization (RICP): Mariani, Alberto, et al. (2004)

Duo-initiator configuration: radical & cation

- Less sensitive to oxygen (as inhibitor), no termination (by combination)
- No limit on UV penetration depth (compare with cationic photopolymerization)

Neopentyl glycol diglycidyl ether as monomer (E)

Benzopinacol as thermal initiator (I)

p-(octyloxyphenyl)phenyliodonium hexafluoroantimonate (IOC8) as superacid generator (A)

Mechanistic Model

R: radicals c: cations e: epoxy functional groups

$$k = A \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right)$$

Simplifications:

1. Omit superacid (SA)

2. Rewrite inhibition step

with f_l : logistic factor

3. Rewrite R and c based on the material balance

$$c = A_0 - A$$

$$R = (I_0 - I) - (A_0 - A)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dt} = -k_d \cdot I$$

$$\frac{dA}{dt} = -f_l \cdot k_a \cdot A \cdot (2 \cdot f \cdot (I_0 - I) - (A_0 - A))$$

$$\frac{de}{dt} = -k_p \cdot e \cdot (A_0 - A)$$

3 steps model

Modelling and DSC measurements with varying formulation and thermal conditions

Solving and parameters fitting in MATLAB

100 monomer (in weight): IOC8 – Benzopinacol

Solid line: experiments
Dash line: 3 steps model

Heating at: 1 K/min, 5 K/min, 10 K/min

↓ exothermic down

Isothermal at: 80 °C, 90 °C, 100 °C

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{e}{e_0}$$

$$\text{Heat Flow} = \frac{dQ}{dt} = H_r \frac{d\alpha}{dt} = -\frac{H_r}{e_0} \frac{de}{dt}$$

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla(\lambda \nabla T) + \rho H_r \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial t}$$

Width: 6 cm; Height: 0.6 cm

Solid domain, without flow & diffusion

$$\rho \text{ (density)}^* = 1130 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3} \quad \lambda \text{ (thermal conductivity)}^* = 0.2688 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}} \quad C_p \text{ (thermal capacity)} = 1.14 \frac{\text{J}}{\text{g}\cdot\text{K}}$$

a: constant temperature 200 °C **d**: Convective heat transfer with external environment at 20 °C.

with heat transfer coefficient $h = 5 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}^2\cdot\text{K}}$

$k_d, k_a, k_p, H_r = 420 \text{ J} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ from kinetic model

Silicon Mold cast with Mold Max™ 60

Type K thermocouples

Fronts initiate with hot plate

e&g: thermal insulation

f: constant temperature at 20 °C

d: Convective heat transfer with external environment at 20 °C.
+ radiative heat transfer with emissivity 0.95.

thermal conductivity of silicone mold = $0.347 \times 1.5 \frac{\text{W}}{\text{m}\cdot\text{K}}$

$$q_{\text{radiation}} \propto \varepsilon(T^4 - T_{\text{amb}}^4)$$

Finite elements modelling

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